

INVISIBLE SCARS: THE LASTING IMPACT OF CHILD ABUSE AND BULLYING

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Annotation: The article deals with the important statistic data about child abuse and bullying in the world. Childhood trauma experience and mental health issues can significantly impact children's emotional development and overall well-being. Traumatic events disrupt their sense of safety and security, leading to heightened levels of fear, anxiety and emotional distress. These experiences can shape their emotional responses and influence their ability to regulate emotions effectively, impacting their overall emotional well-being. In the article invisible scars: the lasting impact of child abuse and bullying was discussed.

Key words: *cognitive health, whistle-blowers, physically bullied, physical appearance, emotional consequences, emotional support, [Psychological abuse](#), Chronic insomnia.*

Babies, Kids, Teens, Adults, and Seniors. Each of these titles represents a season in your life. For kids, that season would be childhood, that magical time between three years old and eleven years old that children take for granted and adults wish they could return to. Childhood is so essential for a child's development that the government stepped in and gave children the right to a childhood. The government passed child labor laws, as well as laws against exploiting children in order to protect them and keep that time of their lives free for healthy play and growth. Play is essential to growth. Areas such as emotional, social, physical, and cognitive health are reliant on childhood play. But today, our children are either giving up or losing their childhood to other pursuits. Having a childhood is one of

the most important areas of life a person can have. It can show kids how to act, what to do and what not to do and so much more. I remember, as a child, playing on the swings and running around with my friends. It was one of the greatest parts of being a kid. The ability to play and use my active imagination with other kids my age.

According to the CDC in the landmark 2014 report [Bullying Surveillance Among Youths](#), estimates of bullying range from 13 to 75 percent. Bullying presents a similar challenge as other forms of abuse and neglect, but is unique in key ways-it is so much a part of our culture, normalized and tolerated, even rewarded and admired as strength and power. Parents of kids who are bullied will tell you that getting recognition and help is often an uphill battle. Teachers are inconsistently trained, school administrators are loathe to recognize issues, whistleblowers get scapegoated, families get ostracized, and victims get blamed. The latest statistics shows that one out of every five (20.2%) students report being bullied[1]. A higher percentage of male than of female students report being physically bullied (6% vs. 4%), whereas a higher percentage of female than of male students reported being the subjects of rumors (18% vs. 9%) and being excluded from activities on purpose (7% vs. 4%). 41% of students who reported being bullied at school indicated that they think the bullying would happen again. Of those students who reported being bullied, 13% were made fun of, called names, or insulted; 13% were the subject of rumors; 5% were pushed, shoved, tripped, or spit on; and 5% were excluded from activities on purpose. A slightly higher portion of female than of male students report being bullied at school (24% vs. 17%). Bullied students reported that bullying occurred in the following places: the hallway or stairwell at school (43%), inside the classroom (42%), in the cafeteria (27%), outside on school grounds (22%), online or by text (15%), in the bathroom or locker room (12%), and on the school bus (8%). 46% of bullied students report notifying an adult at school about the incident. The reasons for being bullied reported most often by students include physical appearance, race/ethnicity, gender, disability, religion, sexual

orientation[2]. The federal government began collecting data on school bullying in 2005, when the prevalence of bullying was around 28 percent. One in five (20.9%) tweens (9 to 12 years old) has been cyberbullied, cyberbullied others, or seen cyberbullying. 49.8% of tweens (9 to 12 years old) said they experienced bullying at school and 14.5% of tweens shared they experienced bullying online. 13% of tweens (9 to 12 years old) reported experiencing bullying at school and online, while only 1% reported being bullied solely online.

The emotional consequences of childhood left-behind experience can manifest in various ways. These children may struggle with trust issues, fearing that others will abandon or betray them. They may experience heightened levels of anxiety, as their sense of safety and security is compromised. These emotional challenges can interfere with their ability to form healthy relationships and regulate their emotions effectively. Moreover, the emotional impact of childhood left-behind experience can extend to other aspects of children's lives, such as their academic performance and social interactions. These children may struggle academically, as their emotional distress can interfere with their concentration, motivation and ability to engage in their studies. They may also face challenges in forming and maintaining meaningful relationships, as they may fear abandonment or struggle to trust others fully. It is crucial to recognize and address the invisible scars left by childhood left-behind experience. Providing emotional support, counseling and therapy can help these children navigate their emotional challenges and develop healthy coping mechanisms. Creating safe and nurturing environments where they can express their emotions, build resilience and establish secure attachments is essential for their emotional healing and overall well-being[3]. Children who have witnessed domestic violence have lasting psychological and emotional effects that follow them into adulthood. [Psychological abuse](#) has stronger effects on a your mental capacity, and [emotional abuse](#) affects what we feel.

Children who are exposed to domestic violence and who are victims of child

abuse, tend to have [low self-esteem](#), and often become [bullies at school](#), or are [bullied by classmates](#). They don't know how to process what they are going through, so they typically act out what they've witnessed at home, in the school yard. Children also tend to [socially withdraw](#) and are deemed "weird" by their peers who don't understand what is going on with their classmate. The teasing by their classmates makes victims more timid, adds trauma on top of trauma, and contributes to the victim hiding and isolating from peers. The way a child is treated at home has a profound effect on how they will do in school. The more abuse they are subjected to, the deeper the trauma. Children aren't equipped with the coping skills to process abuse therefore, they usually express it in inappropriate ways, and sometimes it results in the [victim becoming the aggressor](#). Children who are exposed to violence typically resort to using it in an effort to resolve conflicts and to establish dominance. This can be a defense mechanism, or coping skill to keep from being bullied at school, and teased by peers. Now, we will discuss the effects of bullying:

- Physical trauma- Younger ones are sometimes physically beaten up by the higher grade students. To least extend, they might be poked at the back, threatened or insulted in public. The reason could be any of the above factors; however, as a result, the effects are pretty harmful like a bruise, bleeding, physical injuries and even fracture and sometimes, loss of life.
- Mental trauma- More than physical trauma, the mental wound is more serious and deep, persists for years and hinders a child's healthy development. The possible effects are.
- Chronic insomnia- where the child finds it difficult to get deep sleep due to inherent fear and shame. In fact, [shame](#) was the first moral emotion that drives them crazy. This kind of disturbances is often left unnoticed by the parents. Adequate sleep is highly essential to keep the mind in a calm and steady phase for any individual and at any stage of life. Lack of proper sleep

or having disturbed sleep would have a serious concern on one's health and mind. When such impact starts at childhood, then life will be miserable.

- Inferiority complex- Most often, shame overcome by guilt causing the child to feel inferior on anything and everything. They lack the courage to face the public because of what they had been gone through.
- Being isolated and loneliness- Lack of courage to face people make them prefer all alone and keep themselves away from the crowd or sometimes, with the closed ones like parents and siblings.
- Struggle to socialise- because of bullying and its corresponding traumas, children would find it difficult to mingle with other peers in school and more seriously, it would continue even after they become adult. Their social behavioural skills would be certainly nil or minimal.
- Pessimistic- Mental injuries would desperately make the child to lack positivity. The child tends to see negativity in everything he/she does.
- Decreased cognitive skills- Lack of sleep and other factors would drastically affect the kid's [learning ability](#). Even if the child wishes to learn things, his/her inherent fear would stop doing so. Above that, they neglect to express their suppression to their trustable person thinking that might also end up in bullying. However, this would reflect in their study grade. However, Parents failing to understand this mental trauma would more likely to amplify the injury by insulting the kid for securing a low score.
- Depression and anxiety- Frequent shame and insults would perhaps push a child to chronic depression and anxiety. They become more arrogant and rude to counteract their depression and anger[4].

Bullying is often supported when there is no one to hear kid's grievances. The affected kids hide their feelings of being under stress or even if they want to express it, it mixes with other things, making the cry for help unheard. In such scenarios, teachers and parents should regularly communicate with their children indirectly to

know if there is anything that is bothering them. Different communication channels can be used to bridge the gaps created by formalities. Children in school, due to similar behaviors, form small groups and often create conforming attitudes in these groups. These circles have the potential to develop negative emotions if unchecked. To keep these tendencies out of kid's minds, educators and parents may ask kids to interact with other friends in the class rather than only specific best friends. This also gives a sense of wholesomeness to their character as they listen to other's perspectives.

Kids can better connect with something visual and have a lesson in it. Different art techniques, like drama, posters, or books, can be used to convey what constitutes bullying and the negative impacts it can create for both parties. Putting kids into this simulation can make them understand the ill effects and, due to shared awareness among all the kids, if one sees someone getting bullied, they can stop or report it to their teachers. Kids learn from their surroundings, and what they see they become. Parents and teachers can ensure they don't instill this behavior into the kids by mistake. In schools, these things can develop when a group of teachers with a sarcastic attitude tries to bully a teacher who doesn't conform to their thoughts. This behavior can percolate to kids if not checked. Thus, whenever an educator is in doubt, they can look into their classroom and see if their getting bullied affects their attitude toward children[5]. If it does, they should seek professional help from school management. Using the ideals of famous personalities and taking up lessons from their life can bring in a positive attitude among children. Also, developing leadership skills among kids can make them take responsibility for their actions and thus remove any possibilities of ill behavior from their side. Making kids understand how they have to treat others prevents them from exploring other avenues, respecting the people they talk to, and also showing kindness can stop the egoistic tendencies in the nascent stage.

As a summary it should be noted that nowadays, social media can be a potent

threat when it comes to bullying. Parents can keep notice of how their kids can be targeted through any posts on social media or comments from their friends. Let the kid know that up to a certain age, their texts can be monitored so that they can be kept safe from any mental harassment. In the case of bullying through an online medium, parents should report it to the School and follow up so that such an instance need not be repeated in the future. Being targeted by bullying can be overwhelming for kids, thus first parents and teachers can look out for distress signs in their kids to make them feel wanted. Parents can instill confidence among their kids and make them more resilient towards these attacks. Lastly, following the above steps on how to prevent bullying in school can help you and your child to be more successful in social and academic life and reach their full potential.

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